

Critical Analysis on Education Sector in India

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Abstract

India holds a prominent place in the global education arena. India is home to one of the biggest networks of higher education institutions worldwide. There is still a lot of space for improvement and growth in the educational system. Given that 27% of Indians are between the ages of 0 and 14, the education industry in the nation has numerous opportunities for growth. With 500 million individuals between the ages of 5 and 24, India offers a substantial chance for the education sector to grow globally. Between 2021 and 2025, the Indian market for online education is projected to expand by US\$ 2.28 billion at a CAGR of over 20%. In India, the market expanded by 19.02% in 2021. This paper reflects Critical analysis on Education Sector in India.

Keywords Education, Sector, Pandemic, Quality, Elementary.

Introduction

The Indian Constitution commits the nation to provide quality education to all, and in an effort to meet needs, the government has established various educational level, taking into account the nation's numerous communities and cultures. Different levels in Education are primary and secondary levels, higher education, adult education, and technical and vocational training. Despite significant financial and resource limitations, the nation has developed a very extensive educational system over the past 50 years, producing a sizable population of men and women who are highly skilled in science and technology as well as in humanist and philosophical thought and creativity. It would be interesting to track trends in the various facets of education from the post-Independence era to the current situation.

Objective of study

The Indian education system was advanced since ancient times. It would not be too much to say that India's place was in the first row in terms of education system. Foreigners used to come to India for education. Indian knowledge and science had spread to the world. But later the education system of India collapsed and modern education system was introduced again in the British era. From that time to the present time, I have written this article to comparably highlight the various good and bad aspects of the Indian public and private education system and the government and private education policy. Also through this article, the education system and education policies at every level of India are thoroughly explained. These are the main purposes of writing this short essay. I hope that the purpose of writing this article will be successful and the readers will be appreciated

Review of Literature

Literature is the mirror of society. Various aspects of society are reflected through literature. Nothing can be informed about without literature. Miscellaneous material is collected from literature. Literature not only provides ideas about society, but also gives a clear idea about place, time, state, economy, politics, foreign policy, culture and education policy from literature. Before writing this article, I read some books related to education policy and literature in India and abroad. These books are in Bengali and English. Such as Bengali, Assamese and Rajbangshi languages. I also studied various government gazetteers, reference books, magazines, magazines, periodicals and proceedings and research articles. Some of the important books and journals are : Boyce, E. Mary, "Organizational Learning is Essential to Achieving and Sustaining Change in Higher Education", Ray Land, Agency, context and change in academic

development, International Journal for Academic Development, Barnett, R.(1992), Improving Higher Education, B. Robert Barr & John Tagg, From Teaching to Learning — A New Paradigm For Undergraduate Education, Change : The Magazine of Higher Learning, Contemporary Issues And Challenges In The Indian Education System, Dr. R. N. Nadar, Higher Education in India : Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012-17).

Main Text**Education Sector in India:**

During Independence, only fourteen percent of the population was literate and only one child out of three had been enrolled in primary school. The need for universal education for all children in the age group of 6-14 years recognized as a crucial input for nation building, was given due consideration in successive Five-Year Plans have greatly expanded the geographic reach, infrastructure, and coverage of different social groups; nonetheless, the objective of universal access to basic education remains elusive.

Overview on Elementary Education, Secondary Education, Higher Education, Vocational Education and Technical Education are discussed below :

a. Elementary Education:

Only 1 in 3 children had entered primary school at the time of independence and only 14% of the population was literate. The goal of providing basic education to everyone remains elusive despite the fact that the need for universal education for all children in the age range of 6 to 14 years was recognised as an essential component for nation building. Subsequently Five-Year Plans gave this need due consideration, which led to a vast increase in the geographic reach, infrastructure, and coverage of different social groups.

In accordance with the Indian Constitution, all children up to the age of fourteen must get free and compulsory education. The objective of achieving Universalization of Elementary Education (UEE) during the following ten years i.e., by 1960, was set at the time the Constitution, adopted in the year 1950. The objective was too ambitious to complete in just ten years, especially in light of the country's educational infrastructure at the time. As a result, the target date was changed several times. All attempts were made to provide school facilities up to the year 1960. All programmes pertaining to elementary education in general and primary education in particular are currently focused on the Quality of Education. Over the past fifty years, a lot of work has been done to make elementary education available to everyone.

b. Secondary Education:

Serving as a bridge between elementary and higher education, secondary education helps kids between the ages of 14 and 18 get ready for admission to universities.

In the nation's educational system, secondary education has a very important role to play. It serves as a bridge between primary and higher education. While secondary education helps a person to become a full member of the complex society, primary education is designed to give the bare necessities for existence.

Following independence, our nation had significant, observable changes in the secondary education sector.

A number of committees and commissions were established by the Indian government shortly after the country gained its independence to review the secondary education system.

The numerous committees proposed a number of recommendations for the qualitative and quantitative enhancement of secondary education.

Tara Hand Committees recommended multipurpose secondary schools in 1948 without dissuading from single-purpose schools.

Our secondary education continues to be the weakest link in our educational system and requires urgent change, according to the university education commission report 1948-1949, which was established under the chairmanship of Dr. S. Radhakrishnan. The secondary education commission report from 1952-1953 is a key document in the reconstruction of secondary education in India.

The commission was appointed by the Government of India, on September 23, 1952, under the chairmanship of Dr. A. Lakshmanswami Mudaliar reviewed the shortcomings in secondary education that now exist and offered recommendations for how to make it better.

Under the chairmanship of Dr. A. Lakshmanswami Mudaliar, the commission was appointed by the Government of India on September 23, 1952, to examine the shortcomings in secondary education and provided recommendations for their improvement.

Aims of secondary education according to secondary education commission (1952-53) are :

1. To promote a learner's overall growth.
2. To educate the nation's youth to be law-abiding citizens capable of contributing to the social and economic advancement of the nation.
3. To encourage students' practical skills, intellectual growth, and social qualities.
4. To Train character of students to enable them to participate creatively as citizens in the emerging social order.
5. To improve practical and vocational efficiency of the students.
6. To develop a scientific attitude of mind to think objectively.
7. To inculcate the qualities necessary for living harmoniously and efficiently with one's fellowmen.
8. To develop artistic and cultural interests which are essential for self-expression and development of all round personality of pupils.

Objectives of Secondary education according to Indian Education Commission (1964-66):

1. The main objective is "national reconstruction by raising the standard of living of our people."
2. To meet the needs of a modernizing democratic and socialistic society.
3. To promote productivity.
4. To strengthen social and national integration.
5. To consolidate democracy to adopt as a way of life.
6. To accelerate the pace of modernization.
7. To enable students to participate in productive work in school, home, workshop, farm and factory etc.
8. To develop social, moral and spiritual values among the students.

The Indian Education Commission's proposals led to the reconstruction of education for the nation's economic and cultural development. Secondary education's qualitative growth was given importance through connecting the classroom to the students' actual lives.

c. Higher Education :

In terms of the global higher education network, India has one of the biggest higher education systems, ranking second. "Higher education" in India refers to the post-primary education that lasts two years after the completion of twelve years of formal education

(10 years of elementary education and two years of secondary education). The entire ecosystem of higher education in India, comprising over 1000 universities and almost 42,000 institutions, provides excellent instruction.

These organisations are all governed by the Ministry of Education. India's educational establishments are equipped with state-of-the-art facilities, including libraries and classrooms with smart classrooms, computers, WiFi, and other amenities. All in all, these first-rate resources enable dynamic, 360-degree learning that is advantageous to the pupils. Three Indian institutes have been recognized as being among the best universities in the world: the Indian Institutes of Technology (IITs), Indian Institute of Science (IISc), National Institutes of Technology (NITs), Indian Institutes of Science Education and Research (IISERs), and Indian Institutes of Management (IIMs). This supports the idea that India is growing into a significant education hub for both domestic and international students.

d. Vocational Education (VE)

There have been traditional models of Vocational Education in operation in institutions under Technical education, Pharmacy Council, Nursing Council, Dental Council, Agricultural Council, and the Directorate General of Employment and Training in the Labor Ministry, etc. before the introduction of vocational courses in general schools and colleges at all levels. In addition to the formal sector, adult and volunteer sectors also offered vocational education.

VE was implemented in secondary general education schools, which focus primarily on fundamental academic subjects and have no connection to vocational programmes or apprenticeships. At the +2 and +3 stages of the 10+2+3 general education curriculum, vocational courses were introduced with the dual goals of imparting vocation-specific knowledge and skills.

The following government and non-government institutions currently provide vocational education and training throughout the country:

- a) Schools with a +2 vocational stream;
- b) Industrial Training Institutes (ITIs);
- c) Community Polytechnics;
- d) National Open School;
- e) Open Universities, Selected College / Universities;
- f) Krishi Vigyan Kendras;
- g) Non-Government Organizations; and
- h) Special Institutions. Even though there has been a significant expansion in facilities over the past ten years thanks to new programmes, courses, and institutions, these developments have not been able to keep up with the demands of business, employment, and the general public.

e. Technical education

The country's Technical Education infrastructure has phenomenologically grown over the past five decades, and it has significantly contributed to India's economic and technological development by producing the high-calibre labour force that the country needs for a variety of industries as well as by delivering essential services through research and innovations. Technical institutes and industry have built strong ties. The Technology Development Missions, modernisation and eradication of obsolescence, research and development, etc., are just a few of the new efforts that have been implemented. The focus of technical education is to develop a strong foundation for advanced level work by identifying programmes and courses by institutions, taking into account national and regional needs with a special focus on rural society and disadvantaged sections, and developing horizontal and vertical links with other institutions, research labs, and other organisations. Numerous initiatives have been done by various state governments to advance IT education. Additionally, a number of

innovations are happening beyond the framework of the government. Most of the time, it takes neither a lot of money nor time to replicate such breakthroughs.

Since the time of pre- and post-British rule until the present, a significant change in the educational system has been seen in India. The current education system was first adopted after the Gurukuls, where students were initially educated, were modernised.

Following India's independence, the constitution established six fundamental rights, the Right to Education being one of them. Each and every child between the ages of 6 and 14 was eligible for free schooling.

The primary, secondary, elementary, and pre-primary grades comprise the majority of the educational system. Higher education comes next.

Issues Pertaining to Education System in India:

Discussing below the current issues with the Education system in India:

i. Expenditure :

The improvement of India's educational system requires more funding. Over the last few years, India has made a lot of progress in this regard, and if these continue, it might soon be able to get over its current problems.

ii. India needs to adopt the UN's gross enrolment pattern as well.

iii. Capacity utilisation – The government must push schools to help students succeed, use their abilities to the fullest extent, and not let their ideas go unheard because the world now requires innovative brains.

iv. Infrastructure:

It is necessary to upgrade the infrastructure, particularly in public schools. Government must take action to give the required facilities in government schools and rural areas as they are currently focusing on digital education.

v. PPP Model:

PPPs that are well-designed can produce innovative school systems in India. In light of this, the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) model must be considered.

vi. Student-Teacher Ratio : In comparison to the number of teachers and faculty members accessible, there are significantly more students seeking a quality education. Therefore, in order to educate the future of the country, qualified educators must be hired.

vii. Students Studying Abroad :

Due to problems with the Indian educational system, many students opt to study abroad.

The relevant authorities must address them, and students must decide to remain in India to continue their education and strengthen the nation through their knowledge.

Solutions Pertaining to Issues of Education System in India:

i. Innovations :

This will support the development of students' and the nation's youth's innovative ideas. As a result, the Indian educational system will alter, and the government and authorities need to promote and encourage the next generation of thinkers to prioritize holistic development over rote learning.

ii. Quality of Education :

The level of education offered in rural and urban areas of the nation differs significantly. It is imperative that steps be taken to consistently improve India's educational standards in order to provide everyone with equal access to unbiased information and opportunities for personal development.

iii. Affordability of Education :

There are government schools and educational institutions that are reasonably priced yet fall short in terms of quality and facilities. On the other side, there are several private educational schools that charge exorbitant tuition and have better facilities and study aids. The government must address this discrepancy and make education accessible and cheap for everyone.

Schemes & Campaigns to Boost Education System in India :

List of Government schemes introduced to enhance the education system in India are as follows :

i. Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan –

launched in 2001 with the goal of promoting "Education for All," bolstering the current educational infrastructure, and building new schools. For additional information about the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA), see the linked article.

The National Program for Elementary School Education of Girls -

The Government of India is making a concentrated effort to reach out to the "Hardest to Reach" females, particularly those who are not enrolled in school. Read more at Elementary Education: Moving Towards RTE And Quality Improvement.

i. Mid Day Meal Scheme – It is one meal that is provided to all children enrolled in government schools, government-aided schools, local body schools, special training centres (STC), madrasas and makhtabs supported under Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan (SSA). For further information, go visit the Mid Day Meal Scheme page.

ii. Rashtriya Madhyamik Shiksha Abhiyan – By placing a secondary school within walking distance of every house, this flagship programme hopes to improve secondary education and boost enrollment rates.

iii. Scheme for Infrastructure Development in Minority Institutes – The programme would support minority education by enhancing and bolstering school infrastructure in minority institutions to increase access to formal education for minority youngsters.

iv. Beti Bachao Beti Padhao – The programme to encourage the education of girls in India.

Conclusion

Though the effects of the Covid-19 pandemic have been crippling, undoing years of socio-economic progress and impacting a range of sectors of the country including Education Sector. The government and private bodies are working together to strengthen India's education industry, which is expanding rapidly. The administration is also considering a number of measures to improve India's educational system. Primary education is growing and India is seeing a large influx of foreign schools. In order to provide their children with a high-quality education starting in kindergarten, parents are now enrolling their kids in international schools also.

References

1. Boyce, E. Mary, "Organizational Learning is Essential to Achieving and Sustaining Change in Higher Education", Innovative Higher Education, Vol. 28, No. 2, 2003.
2. Ray Land, Agency, context and change in academic development, International Journal for Academic Development, 6:1, 2001.

3. Barnett,R.(1992).Improving Higher Education: Total Quality Core, Buckingham: SRHE&OU.
4. B. Robert Barr & John Tagg, From Teaching to Learning — A New Paradigm For Undergraduate Education, Change: The Magazine of Higher Learning, Volume 27, Issue 6, 1995.
5. Contemporary Issues And Challenges In The Indian Education System, Dr. R. N. Nadar, ADMIFMS International Management Research Conference 2018
6. Higher Education in India: Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012-17) and beyond FICCI Higher Education Summit 2012.
7. www.ugc.ac.in
8. <https://niti.gov.in/planningcommission.gov.in>